

MEANS OF ORGANIZING AN INTELLIGENT INFORMATION SYSTEM

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Abstract: This article provides formulated information about the design and implementation of the information system, the software product "Information system for personnel management of the department - (e-pedagog.uz)" was obtained, which allows automating the activities of the department of a higher educational institution. The software was fully tested in accordance with the program and test methodology. During testing, a number of errors regarding the correctness of calculations were identified and corrected. The check showed the operability of the system on all declared operating systems, as well as on various hardware platforms in the automation of the work of the department, namely the automation of the management processes of the department. The task of automation is the electronic recording of the individual plans of teachers of a higher educational institution is a key point in the analysis of the work of the entire higher educational institution as a whole. Automation of the process of fulfilling the teaching load by the teacher and filling out an individual plan: will allow you to calculate the theoretical and practical number of hours worked by the teacher

automatically; will reduce the chance of error; control the publication activity of teachers of the department.

Keywords: information system, design, algorithms, models, management system.

1. Introduction

Nowadays, technology is developing rapidly in all areas. This applies to both everyday life and education. The management processes of higher educational institutions in modern conditions are unrealistic without a comprehensive automation of its activities. A higher educational institution is a complex organizational system consisting of an interconnected set of subsystems (types of activity) - educational, scientific, managerial, economic, economic, advertising, considered as objects of management. Therefore, the number of information systems that are used to manage a higher educational institution is currently growing.

Most of these systems are a collection of individual modules: the base of subjects, the educational process, training sessions, exams, the scientific process, messages, system. Information systems include both commercial systems and internal use systems of the organization. An analysis of the available information systems has shown that many of them are designed to facilitate human work.

2. Material and Methods

The purpose of this work is to automate the process of forming and accounting for an individual teacher's plan by developing an information system using the example of the Department of Information Technology in Technical Systems of the Namangan Civil Engineering Institute.

Based on the analysis of the requirements for the creation of the author's system called "Information system for personnel management of the department", the following requirements for the development of an information product were identified:

- the system should provide the ability to enter and store structured information;

- the ability to edit, change and supplement information;
- differentiation of access rights to the system (rector, dean, head of department, lecturer);
- organized storage and automated output for viewing individual plans of teachers and reports on them;
- the ability to quickly and conveniently obtain any necessary statistical information on the selected teacher, the chosen area of work;
- the possibility of automated compilation and printing of individual plans for teachers and reports on them according to a given template.

Based on the requirements for the system, the following were identified as its main functional subsystems: system administration; systems of individual users (deans, heads of departments); faculty administration system.

To work in the system of individual users "Dean of the Faculty", it is necessary to fill in the "Users" menu, this option is available only for users with the "System Administrator" type. To do this, the system administrator performs an initial login to the system using the authorization form (Fig. 1).

After that, by default, the main page is displayed with the appropriate privileges necessary to perform the initial input of user information, in this case, information about the deans of the faculty, as well as setting a login and password for these users. However, after completing the settings, it is better to change it to prevent a violation of the information system. So, the main page of the administrator contains the following tabs: "Users", "Faculties", "Office", "Academic years", "Exit". Adding users is done by clicking on the "Add" button on the "Users" tab. When adding a new user, the system automatically issues an ID number to the entered user. Figure 3 shows the form for filling in the user's data, in this case, information about the deans of the faculty.

Further, the dean user similarly logs into the system using the login and password given to him by the system administrator. The main page of the administrator contains

the following tabs: "Users", "Account", "Statistics of teachers of the department", "Exit". As an administrator in the role of "Dean", the data is entered and the login and password are issued to the head of the department of this faculty. Similarly, the head of the department carries out actions applicable to the faculty of the department (Fig. 2). Users "Dean", "Head of the department", as well as "Teacher" enter personal data into the system by clicking on the "Edit" button and filling in the necessary information: first name, last name, patronymic, term of employment, date and place of birth, nationality, education, specialty by education, academic degree, academic title, knowledge of foreign languages, state awards. This form also contains an entry for filling in work activity, which takes into account the addition of subsequent work activity records by clicking on the "Add" button. After entering personal information, you must click on the "Save" button (Fig.3).

The administration system of the teaching staff is designed to take into account general and personal information about the teachers of the department, plan work according to the individual plan of the teacher for the upcoming academic period, as well as record the implementation of various types of work according to the plan.

To go and launch the main page "Teacher", you must enter using the login and password that was provided to them by the head of the department.

The main page "Teacher" contains the tabs: "Educational work", "Educational and methodical work", "Research work", "Organizational and methodological work", "Spiritual, moral and educational work", "Cabinet", "Exit".

The "Study work" tab contains the "Add" button for entering the study load, "Study periods", "Types of semesters (autumn, spring)", a table for filling in the study load by teachers according to the plan (subject name, additional information, study work (lecture, practice, laboratory classes, term paper, thesis, scientific research management), as well as accounting for work performed, unscheduled work and

incentive points, crediting fines). To fill in the entries, you must click on the "Add" button.

Fig.1. Authorization form

Fig.2. Form for entering user information and setting a password, as a system administrator

Fig.3. Form for filling in personal data of users

The “Research work” tab contains the “Add” button for introducing a research plan by the teacher based on the types of activities and time standards (for example: preparation and publication of a scientific article, dissertation, invention (patent), creation of software tools; publication of monographs, preparation of information and analytical materials, creation of creative works; publishing a catalog of personal (thematic) creative works, creating new projects; editing textbooks, monographs and teaching aids; conducting research work on a topic approved by the university council; writing reviews of textbooks, teaching aids, monographs, brochures, scientific articles, dissertations, abstracts and other works; preparation and defense of a dissertation for the degree of Doctor of Philosophy (PhD), Doctor of Science (DSc); membership in the editorial board of scientific journals; management of research and scientific and creative work students; organization of scientific or methodological conferences and seminars; participation in scientific or methodological councils, etc.). It contains "Study periods", as well as a "Table" for teachers to fill in (name of the work performed, the term and completion of work according to the plan, the amount of work according to the plan and their implementation, points scored, as well as unscheduled work and incentive points, crediting fines). To fill in the entries, click on the "Add" button. It turns out that the following form, in which you need to enter the name of the planned work, the deadline and the amount of hours (Fig.4).

The screenshot shows a CRM interface for 'Research activities'. It includes a sidebar with navigation options like 'Research activities', 'Add new', 'Filter', and 'Export'. The main area displays a table with columns for 'ID', 'Name of the work', 'Start date', 'End date', 'Status', 'Points scored', 'Points to be scored', 'Points to be scored', 'Points to be scored', and 'Points to be scored'. The table contains one row of data with the following values: ID: 1, Name of the work: Подготовка монографии, Start date: 2023-01-01, End date: 2023-01-01, Status: В работе, Points scored: 1, Points to be scored: 1.

ID	Имя работы	Дата начала	Дата окончания	Статус	Получено баллов	Назначено баллов	Получено баллов	Назначено баллов	Получено баллов
1	Подготовка монографии	2023-01-01	2023-01-01	В работе	1	1	1	1	1

The form is a web-based interface for entering research papers. It features several input fields and a dropdown menu. At the top left, there is a text input field. To its right is a dropdown menu labeled 'Учебный год' (Academic year) with '2022-2023' selected. Below these are two more input fields: 'Зарубежные*' (Foreign) and 'Республиканские*' (Republican), both containing '0'. A section header 'according to plan' is centered below these fields. Underneath, there are two more input fields: 'Срок*' (Term) and 'Объем работы*' (Volume of work), both containing '0'. At the bottom of the form is a green 'save' button.

Fig.4. Form for entering research papers of a teacher

The “Organizational and methodological work”, “Spiritual, moral and educational work” tabs contain the “Add” button for introducing a plan for these types of work (for example: helping a student go through the process of adapting to new conditions when entering a university and correctly allocating his time in period of stay at the university; holding meetings to develop the student's personal and academic achievements; forming an understanding of the importance of the impact of grades and knowledge gained by students on their qualification level; working with students' parents; monitoring the work of graduates; conducting career guidance for students for admission to higher educational institutions; preparing students to receive state scholarships, international and republican Olympiads, competitions, organization and holding of sports, cultural, educational and creative events, etc.). It contains "Study periods", as well as a "Table" for teachers to fill in (name of work performed, deadline and completion of work according to the plan, scope of work according to the plan and their implementation, venue, points scored, as well as unscheduled work and incentive points, enrollment fines). To fill in the entries, click on the "Add" button. The following form appears, in which it is necessary to enter the name of the planned work, the deadline and the amount of hours.

3. Result

To develop a rating system, legal and regulatory documents were analyzed, as well as rating systems in higher educational institutions. In developing the assessment system, we identified the following patterns:

- Both positive (for unscheduled work) and negative points (penalties) are allowed;

- When evaluating individual indicators, the position, academic degree of the teacher (head of the department, professor, associate professor, senior lecturer, assistant) was taken into account;

- assessment is taken into account in units of measurement - points;

- indicators of evaluation of the teacher's activity - educational work, educational and methodological work, research work, organizational and methodological work, spiritual, moral and educational work. For each indicator, the calculation rules are determined, which include (receipt of points for academic work - 25 points, educational and methodological work - 25 points, research work - 30 points, organizational and methodological work - 10 points, spiritual, moral and educational work - 10 points Total 100 points);

- the rating of teachers is taken into account according to the rules for determining the teaching load of the teaching staff of a higher educational institution and educational, methodological, research and "mentoring" work, approved by the Ministry of Higher and Secondary Specialized Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan;

- taking into account the distribution of the amount of work by co-authors, i.e. division of points for all co-authors for a scientific article, monograph, study guide, etc.;

- taking into account the adjustment of the assessment by indicators (previously recorded achievements, inconsistencies between the files uploaded to the system for

the implementation of plans for the types of activities of the teacher, etc.), as well as entering into the system comments, warnings on the work performed by the teacher.

To display the general statistics of the teachers of the department, on the main page "Head of the Department" go to the tab "Statistics of the teachers of the department" where you can view statistics about the teachers of the department based on their rating.

Thus, the developed information system for managing the personnel of the department will significantly reduce the time spent on processing and analyzing the activities of teachers according to individual plans, organize management processes more efficiently, improve the quality of analysis of the activities of the teaching staff, reduce the time spent on these operations, and reduce the number of errors. caused by the "human factor". The developed system was successfully implemented in the activities of the department "Information technologies in technical systems" of the Namangan Civil Engineering Institute, which made it possible to reduce the time for analysis and data collection when planning the activities of the department by the head, since now there is no need to manually view all the individual plans of teachers in the format MS Excel, Word and collect the necessary data from them, this function is now performed by the developed system. Undoubtedly, the use of information technology in human activities saves a lot of time, and also eliminates the so-called human factor, that is, mistakes made by a person, for example, due to inattention, which has an extremely negative effect on the quality of the work performed.

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3. Acknowledgements:

This article provides clearly formulated information, which summed up the software product "Information system for personnel management of the department - (e-pedagog.uz)" in the process of working design and implementation of the system, which allows automating the activities of the department of higher educational institutions. The software was fully tested in accordance with the program and test methodology. During testing, a number of errors regarding the correctness of calculations were identified and corrected. The test showed that the system works on all declared operating systems, as well as on various hardware platforms.

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